

Phonological Domains in Hixkaryana

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Primary Source(s)

Derbyshire, Desmond C. 1979. *Hixkaryana*. Amsterdam: North Holland Publications.
Derbyshire, Desmond C. 1985 *Hixkaryana and Linguistic Typology*. Dallas: Summer
Institute for Linguistics Publications in Linguistics; 76.

I. Author's definitions of p-words:

contain one or more gwords

"whose defining feature is that it is bounded by pause" (1979, p. 182)

and where syllable assignment and vowel length rule apply within pwords,
across gword boundaries

II. Notes on Syllable Structure (general)

Basic template: (C)CV(C)

the syllable boundary is always after the first C in three consonant clusters (refers to
gwords)

V and VC occur only pword-initial, never medial, and no pword ends with a syllable
that is V-only or VC only

- (1) a.na.ro "another"
om.sam.txe.mo "young girl"

*Language Reporter note: the syllable template that refers to the minimal pword is bigger than the
CCVC one above. It is actually more like (C)V(C).CV--disyllabic. This is based on looking at his
glossary. Almost every word that is treated as its own phonological unit has this size.*

III. Syllable Structure Constraints & Observed Phonotactic Patterns

There are restrictions on gword-medial clusters, e.g.

/p/ never cluster-initial, only follows /m/ and /h/ within one gword

/f/ only precedes /r/, /ry/, /y/ within gword

/f/ only follows /r/, /ry/, /y/, /n/ within gword

there are no geminate clusters in gwords

/k/ never precedes voiceless nonsyllabic except /h/ within gword

/h/ never follows /m/, /h/, /s/, /x/ within gword

*Language Reporter note: these restrictions should be clarified with respect to specific
morphological structure*

The pword never begins with a c-cluster, and never ends with a c-cluster. Clusters
permitted medially, but subject to varying restrictions

cluster-medial example:

/waja:mo-tʃko/ 'turtle-dimin' (in this case the affricate resyllabifies to be coda of

preceding syllable) [waja:moɬf.ko]

Researcher Question: Are all such medial clusters redsyllabified to C.C? If so, this reflects a general ban on onset and coda clusters, anywhere.

IV. P-Rules & Processes, and the Morpho-Syntactic Information they Reference

There are general vowel and C assimilation processes--again complex in their distribution. However, they are always applicable within boundaries of pword and never apply across the edges of a pword.

There is a paltalization or poa backing process: r > ry; t > tʃ or n > ɲ when adjacent to /e/ at a morpheme boundary. This happens only within the pword, and not at edges when, for example, n is adjacent to another word that begins or ends with /e/. In this way, the process is confined to pword-medial.

- (2) w-onye-tano > ([wenytʃano])
1-see-IMPER 'let me go see it!'

There is a V lengthening rule: in a 2-syllable word, if both syllables are CV, then the initial syllable V > V:

- (3) kwaja > [kwa:ja] 'red & green macaw'

In polysyllabic words, every even-numbered syllable starting from the left edge of the pword EXCEPT FINAL syllable will lengthen:

- (3) nemokotono > [nemo:koto:no] 'it fell'

This lengthen rule may cross morpheme boundaries, as long as they are all part of same pword, because the final vowel never lengthens. disyllabic suffixes may participate in this rule, as may post-positions

- (4) ow.to + ho.na > [ow.to:honaɛ]
village + to 'to the village'
- (5) toh.ku.rye + ho.na > [toh.ku:ryi.ho:na]
place.name + to 'to the place-name village'

There is a somewhat complicated process of vowel deletion, but it happens only within the pword boundaries--never at end or start. It may cross morpheme boundaries, as long as the 2 morphemes constitute 1 pword.

- (6) (ki-oti-ma-no) > [kotmano]
1/2-meat-BEN-PST 'I gave you meat'

A specific process of i/u vowel deletion (perhaps different from the one just described):

if in a prefix-stem combination or in a stem stem or stem-suffix combination, the prefix or stem vowels deleted:

- (7) ni-amuku-no 3S3o-pick.up-IMMPST > [namukno] 'he picked it up'
tohu=oni > stone this [tohoni] 'this is a stone'

an h > [p] alternation

happens to the stem in a stem-suffix combo

- (8) t-imi-hira GEN-PREF-give-NEG > [timpira] 'not giving it' (
Reporter note: It looks like i is deleted too, crucially ordered before?)

happens to the 2nd stem in a stem-stem combo

- (9) tamusnyem heno > [tamusnyempeno] 'the dead heavy thing'

as long as (in both cases) the stem ends in h or m
not totally regular here.

Two kinds of vowel harmony:

A. i > [u] in a prefix-stem-suffix combo

- (10) mi-hutjuhka-no 2S3O-take.off.skin-IMMPST > [muhutjuhkanu] 'you took off the
skin'
ro-onu-ri 1-EYE-POSS > [ronuru] 'my eye'

B. o > [a] in a prefix-stem combo or a proclitic-stem combo

- (11) o-manho-no 2S-dance-IMMPST > [amanhono] 'you danced'
ohfehra mo=naye not-well 3OUTOFSIGHT=she.is > [manaye] 'she is not well'

Stress Patterns

While stress plays no morpho-syntactic role, it helps to define the P-word domain:
primary stress: on final syllable of pword
secondary stress on first VC or V: syllable

Reduplication

There seems to be reduplication only in some ideophones, but it is not described in detail by Derbyshire, therefore the details are currently not known

V. The available morpheme types in Hixkaryana include:

stem

pro-clitic/pre-posed particles

discourse particles with post-posed occurrence restrictions (post-posed particles)

suffixes

prefixes

Language Reporter note: not sure if enclitic/post-posed particle attested?